

INTERLINEAR TRANSLATION

ACROSS THE MUSLIM WORLD

A Comparative Perspective

Themed Section

edited by

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Interlinear Texts from Indonesia: *Preliminary Thoughts on Their Study*

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Abstract

Interlinear translations have been known in Indonesia's Islamic communities since at least the late 16th century with extant evidence in the form of manuscripts pointing to their ongoing popularity in the following centuries. Such translations encompass important works composed in Arabic and rendered in the languages of the archipelago, and they touch upon key fields of knowledge, among them Islamic law, theology and grammar. But has this textual abundance been matched by the range of scholarly writings produced about this phenomenon? This paper asks if and how interlinear texts from Indonesia were studied by scholars in the nineteenth and twentieth centuries. It does not attempt to offer an exhaustive survey but rather raises questions about how interlinear translations were perceived and points to possible trends that have helped shape the scholarly context for the Textual Microcosms project, currently exploring interlinear translation across the Indonesian-Malay world.

Keywords: Indonesia, Java, Interlinear translation, colonial scholarship, pesantren

Introduction

Indonesia is a vast, multilingual and multicultural archipelago and has been a crossroads of religious ideas and practices for many centuries. The history of Islam in the region goes back to at least the 13th century and likely earlier and Islam is now the religion of approximately 90% of Indonesia's citizens. Arabic texts, above all the Qur'an but also legal, ritual, historical and hagiographical texts of diverse origins in their original, adapted and translated forms played a central role in the process of Islamization which unfolded gradually across the region. In the long process of Islamization translation and education played major roles. Interlinear translation—the addition of a translation in between the lines of a text—reflected

¹ I thank the Israel Science Foundation (grant no. 2009/19) and the European Research Council Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (Grant agreement No. CoG 101001731) for generously funding the research on which this study is based. My thanks go also to all participants in the "Interlinear Translation Across the Muslim World" workshop, to my co-editor Dr Fadhli Lukman and to Tony Day, for their insightful and constructive comments.

a linking of the two as it was used to teach both the Arabic language and the doctrines and rituals of the faith.

This article emerged from on-going research on interlinear translation in the Indonesian-Malay world, understood as a translation method, a historical and living practice, and a site of a range of encounters. A site where two languages meet one another, where ideas, beliefs and textual histories of one culture approach another's, teacher and disciple interact, and colors, ink types, scripts and frames structure visual encounters on a page. How was this phenomenon studied by others, especially early on, and what assumptions about it might we have inherited, I wondered.

Interlinear translations have been known in Indonesia's Islamic communities for several centuries with extant evidence in the form of manuscripts pointing to their ongoing popularity from the late sixteenth century. Such translations encompass important works composed in Arabic and rendered in the languages of the archipelago, and they touch upon key fields of knowledge, among them Islamic law, theology, sufism and grammar.²

In thinking about interlinear translation from Arabic to local languages two initial questions that emerge are which languages were used to produce the translations and how significant were Islamic interlinear translations in the Indonesian archipelago.³ Within the vast, diverse and multi-lingual archipelago the two languages that stand out are Malay and Javanese, used more often than other languages to provide an interlinear translation of Arabic texts, although translations into Sundanese, Bugis, Makassarese, Madurese and additional languages were produced as well.⁴ Regarding the significance of interlinear translations from this region two types of evidence stand out in particular: chronological and quantitative. I begin with chronology.

One of the earliest known Arabic-Malay interlinear exemplars is found in a manuscript of Islamic Creed (*'Aqā'id*) by al-Nasafi dated 1590, while the Arabic to Malay *al-Burda* was inscribed in 1600 at the latest.⁵ Indonesian manuscripts from the sixteenth century are rare, making both of these manuscripts among the oldest Malay (and more generally Indonesian) manuscripts of any genre extant. Other early examples include early 17th century fragments from the Arabic poem *Bad'i al-āmāli*, a beginner's treatise on theology with interlinear Malay translation, and an early 18th century treatise on marriage, *Ahkām al-nikāh*, also with

2 Azyumardi Azra, "Naskah Terjemahan Antarbaris: Kontribusi Kreatif Dunia Islam Melayu-Indonesia." In *Sadur: Sejarah Terjemahan di Indonesia dan Malaysia*, ed. Henri Chambert-Loir (Gramedia, 2009), 435–443.

3 Using "Indonesia," and also "the Indonesian archipelago" are of course anachronisms as the state was founded in 1945, but I will use them here for the sake of brevity and convenience. There are additional, non-Islamic traditions of interlinear translation in the archipelago, however in this article my focus is for the most part on Islamic texts.

4 Malay was the most important language to the spread of Islam in the region, a lingua franca of trade, travel, diplomacy and religious teaching. Javanese was the language of the largest ethnic group and one that possessed a literary and religious writing tradition going back to at least the 9th century.

5 On the former see S. M. N. Al-Attas, *The Oldest Known Malay Manuscript: a 16th century Malay Translation of the 'Aqā'id of Al-Nasafi* (University of Malaya, 1988). On the latter see G.W. J. Drewes, *Een 16de Eeuwse Maleische Vertaling van de Burda van al-Busiri (Arabisch Lofdicht op Mohammad)* (Martinus Nijhoff, 1955).

interlinear Malay translation.⁶

In the case of Arabic to Javanese, the earliest known exemplar of interlinear translation from Arabic is said to be the *Masā'il al-ta'lim*, dated 1623 at the latest and housed at the British Library (see Fig. 1).⁷ Another, possibly even earlier example is a copy of *al-Īdāh* from the collection of Jan Theunisz (d. 1638) currently at the Library of the University of Amsterdam.⁸ Both are works on jurisprudence (*fiqh*). The fact that some of the earliest surviving manuscripts still extant from the archipelago are in the form of interlinear translations is telling and suggests this form of writing may have been among the first to circulate as Islam was taking hold in the region. At the very least these dated manuscripts

Fig. 1 *Masā'il al-ta'lim*, Arabic with Javanese translation and notes, 1623. British Library, [Sloane 2645, ff. 6v–7r](#)

- 6 Both are discussed by Ph. S. van Ronkel, on which see more below. Ph. S. van Ronkel, "Account of Six Malay Manuscripts of the Cambridge University Library," *Bijdragen tot de taal-, land- en volkenkunde* 46, no. 1 (1896): 1–53, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1163/22134379-90000076>. There are also examples from the archipelago of early interlinear translations from Persian into Malay, but these lie outside the purview of this article. On such examples see Majid Daneshgar, "Persianate Aspects of the Indonesian-Malay World: Some Rare Manuscripts in the Leiden University Library," *Dabir*, no. 8 (2021): 51–78.
- 7 Bernard Arps and Annabel Teh Gallop, *Golden Letters: Writing Traditions of Indonesia/Surat Emas: Budaya Tulis di Indonesia* (The British Library; Yayasan Lontar, 1991), 100; I. Yahya, M.A.K. Hassan, dan Farkhan, *Penerjemahan Manuskrip Masā'il al-ta-Ta'lim ke dalam Aksara Pegon pada Abad ke-17 M* (IAIN Surakarta Press, 2018).
- 8 This is manuscript I H 1. Muhammad Dluha Lutfillah, Personal communication, January 2025.

offer concrete evidence for interlinear translations having been created and read during this early period.

In addition to the chronologically important evidence of very early surviving manuscripts there is quantitative evidence of the prevalence of interlinear translation from libraries at Islamic boarding schools (*pesantren* in Java, *surau* in Sumatra) whose collections have been digitized by the Endangered Archives Programme and DREAMSEA initiatives, as well as from an in-progress database that draws on Indonesian manuscript collections in the British Library, Leiden University, the National Library of Indonesia, and more (for an example see Fig. 2).⁹

Fig. 2 Nazm poem. Arabic with Malay translation, 1870s, Palembang, Sumatra. [DS 0005 0002](#)

9 For the Endangered Archives Programme see <https://eap.bl.uk/>. For pesantren collections see, for example, <https://eap.bl.uk/collection/EAP061-1> (from Langitan) and <https://eap.bl.uk/collection/EAP061-2> (Kranji). For DREAMSEA see <https://dreamsea.co/>.

Hence we know that interlinear translations circulated early on and that, in certain educational contexts, they were numerous. We also know that most extant manuscripts in Indonesia generally (and in collections of Indonesian manuscripts outside Indonesia, e.g., in Leiden, Kuala Lumpur, London), and also specifically those from pesantren, date from the 19th century. This is important because the height of colonial scholarly production about Indonesian religions, languages and cultures was in the nineteenth and first half of the twentieth centuries, suggesting that there was no dearth of interlinear translations to be examined and studied during this period. Did this phenomenon inspire interest and curiosity among scholars? What evidence is available on inquiries into the practice and its implications?

To consider these questions this article explores how interlinear translation was addressed in scholarship on Indonesia, with a focus on the 19th and early 20th centuries: what was written about it, and by whom? How was the practice described and understood? What significance was attached to it, if any? It offers a preliminary survey and tentative thoughts about how interlinear translations were perceived during this period and points to possible trends that have helped shape the scholarly context for the Textual Microcosms project, currently exploring interlinear translation across the Indonesian-Malay world.¹⁰

Where are the Interlinear Translations?

Working within the framework of Textual Microcosms and considering various approaches to the study of interlinear translation raised the question of how earlier researchers viewed these texts. The search for interlinear texts and for their explication and analysis in scholarship turned out to be more challenging than I had expected, as outlined in the following pages.

In what may be one of the early mentions of interlinear translation in a scholarly publication the famed Dutch linguist H. N. van der Tuuk, writing in the Leiden-based journal *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde (BKI)* in 1866, mentioned an Arabic to Malay interlinear translation of al-Samarkandi's *Bayān 'aḳīdah al-uṣūl* (commonly known in Indonesia by its author's name) in a brief report he published on various Malay manuscripts.¹¹ There was no detailed description or discussion, but the author was clearly familiar with this popular text and noted that interlinear translations of al-Samarkandi into Javanese in west Java were "numerous" and that there was also, in Batavia, a commentary on the text which had an interlinear translation in Javanese. Finally, he mentioned that he was in the possession of two such commentaries in Sundanese.¹² Based on this fleeting note we can conclude that

¹⁰ For more on Textual Microcosms, a European Research Council Horizon 2020 project (CoG 101001731) see <https://textualmicrocosms.huji.ac.il/>.

¹¹ H. N. van der Tuuk, "Aanteekeningen," *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 13, no.1 (1866): 466–467. This was in fact a set of "Notes." Mention of the interlinear translation text occurred within a survey of various manuscripts, including a section on manuscripts from the Indian Office in London that were previously held at the East India House.

¹² Sundanese is spoken in the western part of Java. It is not clear from Van der Tuuk description whether

Van der Tuuk was familiar with the phenomenon, with interlinear translations from Arabic into two or three languages (Malay, Javanese, possibly Sundanese), and with their popularity. There is nothing in his brief paragraph that expresses any surprise or special interest or insight.

Fifteen years later, writing in the same journal, the philologist A. W. T. Juynboll discussed an Arabic to Javanese interlinear translation of the same text, which he had translated into Dutch. His article, which contained only two pages written by him and ten pages of the interlinear text, was titled “A Muslim catechism in Arabic with a Javanese interlinear translation in *Pegon* script.”¹³ All we learn about the manuscript on which his translation was based is that it was brought by one of his students from Java to Holland, and that large parts of it were eaten up by ants.¹⁴ Although Juynboll highlighted the interlinear translation in his article’s title, he seemed interested in authorship, content and textual versions but said nothing of the translation method, its uses or implications. The Dutch translation he produced referred only to the Arabic text, ignoring the potential meanings and nuances of the Javanese interlinear translation and its use as a pedagogical and cultural phenomenon. Although this remains unacknowledged, the Dutch in fact replaced the Javanese as the translation language.

In the same *BKI* volume Juynboll published three more brief articles on the *Samarkandi*, titled “The Samarkandi Catechism Reviewed” parts I, II and III.¹⁵ In the first he explained that he recently came across a manuscript with the Arabic Samarkandi text and a commentary on it that helped him better understand it and therefore he was able to improve his earlier Dutch translation and he decided to publish this Arabic text. In part II he republished his Dutch translation, and in part III are found his notes, which address several points appearing in the Arabic text and also discussed in the commentary (e.g., the angels, God’s throne, God’s oneness). No further mention is made of the interlinear translation and one can contrast the ongoing interest of Juynboll in the Arabic text and his attempts to read and re-read it, along with the helpful commentary (which could have been compared to the Javanese translation, asking, for example, if there were any echoes of the commentary within the translation) with

the Sundanese text contains an interlinear translation or just commentaries. Van der Tuuk, “Aanteekeningen,” 467.

- 13 A.W.T. Juynboll, “Een Moslimsche catechismus in her Arabisch met eene Javaansche interlineare vertaling in pegonschrift,” *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 29 (1881): 215–227. Juynboll wrote that “Since the Arabic text is not entirely complete, and there are also gaps in the Javanese interlinear translation, I have tried to consult more manuscripts of this work, but so far without result,” a comment that shows that he likely relied at least somewhat on the translation to understand the Arabic. “Nevertheless,” he continued, “I believe that this edition should not be postponed, but on the contrary can be useful, since for many people there may be a good opportunity to compare other copies with the text given here, so that this provisional edition can soon be replaced by a better one. That is why I only give here the Arabic and Javanese text with a simple translation, without further explanation, which will certainly not be lacking in a later edition.” *Ibid.*, 215.
- 14 The translation into Dutch appears in the same volume: A.W.T. Juynboll, “Een Moslimsche catechismus in het Arabisch met eene Javaansche interlineare vertaling in pegonschrift uitgegeven en in het Nederlansch vertaald,” *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 29 (1881): 229–231.
- 15 A.W.T. Juynboll, “Samarkandi’s Catechismus opnieuw besproken,” I, II, III, *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 29 (1881): 267–274, 275–278, 279–284, respectively.

his silence on the Javanese rendering of this important work to which, at least in these writings, he did not seem to attach significance.

It is worthy of note that in both the initial article (see note 13) and in his “Review part I” Juynboll expressed some hesitation about publishing on *al-Samarkandi* without reviewing and comparing additional exemplars for detail and depth but decided nonetheless to go forward with the rationale that even partial scholarship on these texts is important and would assist others with access to similar sources, yet none of his considerations touch on the existence of the interlinear translation.

During approximately the same period the work of Ph. S. van Ronkel stands out for his interest in the practice and his attentiveness to the detail that is among the hallmarks of interlinear translation. In an 1896 article describing six manuscripts housed at the Cambridge University library he discussed two that included interlinear texts and commented in detail on several of their dimensions.¹⁶ Possibly following that work, as well as an examination of additional manuscripts he encountered, Van Ronkel several years later (1899) published what constituted a pioneering attempt to survey the interlinear practice and map its far-reaching effects.¹⁷

Van Ronkel’s main claim, based on a range of interlinear translation examples, was that there was a striking uniformity in the way Malay scholars and scribes translated Arabic words, idioms, and grammatical particles, such as prepositions, into Malay. He showed how they also tended to standardize the way in which markers of gender, number, and tense—omnipresent in Arabic but not in Malay—were rendered in a manner that could be understood and internalized by the texts’ audiences. Further, he claimed that interlinear translation not only impacted content and the way vocabulary was appropriated or adapted in a new language and culture, but also that such translations were a powerful influence on recasting the more subtle realm of Malay syntax. For example, he found that the Arabic preposition *bi* was consistently translated as *dengan*, and so the phrase *bismillāh* (in the name of God) was translated into Malay as *dengan nama Allah*, rather than the conventional *atas nama Allah*. Moreover, Van Ronkel showed also how various irregular constructions in Malay can be understood if retranslated (i.e., “translated backwards”) into Arabic. Such patterns were then gradually assimilated into texts that were not interlinear translations, generalized and incorporated into the Malay language, and gaining a life of their own that was no longer dependent on a detailed translation strategy. Using Arabic syntax to write Malay thus gradually became more habitual, so much so that it is clearly visible in examples taken from the Malay *hikayat* genre, often recounting tales of love, adventure, and travel that have little to do explicitly with religion.¹⁸

16 Van Ronkel, “Account of Six Malay Manuscripts,” 1–53.

17 Ph. S. van Ronkel, *Mengenai Pengaruh Tatakalimat Arab Terhadap Tatakalimat Melayu*, trans. A. Ikram, Seri Terjemahan Karangan-karangan Belanda (Bhratara, 1977). First published as “Over de Invloed der Arabische Syntaxis op de Maleische,” *Tijdschrift voor Indische Taal- Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 41 (1899): 498–528.

18 A similar process was most likely taking shape in Javanese, through interlinear translations from Arabic. For a discussion of an example that points to how “interlinear translation Javanese” was employed in Javanese-only literature, see Ronit Ricci, “Mediating the Maulid: Interlinear Translations of the *Maulid Syaraf al-Anām* Across the Indonesian-Malay World,” *Indonesia and the Malay World* 51, no.150 (2023):

Van Ronkel was very much aware that by considering interlinear translation from Arabic into Malay in a systematic way—unlike earlier studies of specific texts—he was entering uncharted waters, delving into a topic that had not yet been articulated, much less so explored.¹⁹ He understood interlinear translation as a profoundly important practice that shaped the Malay language anew. In his view it reshaped the language as it appeared in the interlinear translations but, beyond this prevalent but specific usage, it also transformed Malay much more broadly, in the writing of other texts and eventually, in all likelihood, in speech. His remains a seminal study, with its importance lying both in the many details and examples provided and in the kinds of questions raised, the phenomena noticed and the depth of engagement.²⁰

Snouck Hurgronje, a key scholar-administrator of the late 19th century Dutch East Indies,²¹ also addressed the practice and pedagogy of interlinear translation. During his stay in Mecca (1884–1885) he spent much of his time with the Jawah community, documenting their lives there. He distinguished between two pedagogical methods for teaching pilgrims from the archipelago Arabic and Islamic texts: in Java, he wrote, people studied from books written in Javanese or Malay or they began without any preparation to read small introductory works in Arabic to which they added a translation between the lines based on their teacher's words. In Mecca, on the other hand, Javanese and Malay were used consistently as a means to introduce students to Arabic, particularly to its grammar, so that gradually they gained enough knowledge, through constant translation and interpretation into their own language, to be able to read books of law and doctrine in Arabic. Snouck very clearly prioritized the Meccan method based on the study of Arabic grammar and syntax via interlinear translation as opposed to learning bits of Arabic by rote. He called the Javanese method “pitiful” and stated that in some areas, notably west Java, Arabia-trained teachers were gaining the upper hand for the Arab method which “should gradually drive out the older systems of teaching.”²² His depiction offers important insights on the use of interlinear translation and raises questions about it, perhaps above all about whether it could be a practice that developed in Arabia—in Mecca—and not in Indonesia.

His writing also touched upon a suggested hierarchy of Indonesian languages vis-a-vis Arabic, claiming that only Malay and Javanese fully attained the status of a “speech of Moslim civilization,” while Madurese, Buginese and Makassarese attained it to some degree

143–164. DOI: 10.1080/13639811.2023.2221927

19 Van Ronkel, *Mengenai Pengaruh Tatakalamat*, 12.

20 Although Van Ronkel passed away many years later, in 1954, I was unable to find evidence of another major work of his on this topic. For a list of his publications see P. Voorhoeve, “Bibliografie der Geschriften van Prof. Dr. Ph. S. van Ronkel,” in *Bingkisan Budi, een bundel opstellen aan Dr. Philippus Samuel Van Ronkel door vrienden en leerlingen aangeboden op zijn tachtigste verjaardag* (A. W. Sijthoff's Uitgeversmaatschappij N.V., 1950), 346–354.

21 On Snouck Hurgronje see, for example, Léon Buskens, Jan Just Witkam and Annemarie van Sandwijk, eds., *Scholarship in Action: Essays on the Life and Work of Christiaan Snouck Hurgronje (1857–1936)* (Brill, 2022). <https://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500.12657/87102>

22 Christiaan Snouck Hurgronje, *Mekka in the Latter Part of the 19th Century: Daily Life, Customs and Learning, the Moslims of the East-Indian-Archipelago. 1888–1889* (E. J. Brill, 1931), 283–286.

and Sundanese, Acehnese and others not at all. This claim he based on his observation that there was a large number of translations of Arabic works into Malay and Javanese as well as a variety of compilations, commentaries and a rich popular literature in these languages which was independent of the Arabic, while the other languages “have shown themselves as suitable garb for Islam in much less degree.” Those speaking Madurese, Buginese or Makassarese had to learn Javanese or Malay in order to enter the fields of Islamic knowledge, if Arabic proved too difficult. Most coming from Lampung, Aceh, Sumbawa and elsewhere studied via Malay while the Sundanese of west Java typically did so through Javanese, even while still in Indonesia, and in Mecca had a choice between the two languages and “at most the beginners gain help in understanding only from a few short notes or fragmentary interlinear translations in their mother-tongue, dictated by some teacher from their own district.”²³ It is important to consider possible implications of Snouck Hurgronje’s comments on the link between the level of Arabic and Islamic piety among different linguistic groups (whether real or perceived) on the history of scholarship. His observations about Javanese and Malay are relevant to any discussion of the volume and range of interlinear translations into these languages as compared with others, at least within the extant archive.

Snouck Hurgronje’s two-volume *The Acehnese*, was written after his book on Mecca and with the perspective he had gained there, observing and interpreting what he saw in Aceh, at least in part, through that earlier lens.²⁴ In *The Acehnese* volume 2 he offered a comparison between the method practiced “since ancient times” by Javanese and Sundanese Muslim wishing to study the Arabic books of law and doctrine and the method practiced in Aceh by those who wished to be considered as *ulama*. He began by describing how the Javanese pupil read a sentence which was then translated literally into Javanese (and the translation language differed greatly from that of daily life), with Arabic technical terms left untranslated. The word-for-word translation (*ma’na* or *logat*) was followed by an explanatory paraphrase (*murad*). He concluded that the Javanese remained patient with this method because they took pleasure in reading the authoritative Arabic text in the original, with the subsequent word-for-word literal translation removing all doubt—so he believed—regarding the meaning of the Arabic words. The Sundanese, he added, followed the same method but in their case only the *murad* was given in their language.²⁵

Snouck Hurgronje then moved on to the other method, the one he had also seen in Mecca, which over the previous thirty to forty years “gained supremacy in Java under Mekkan and Hadramite influence” which is “more logical but requires much greater patience and perseverance.” This involved studying Arabic grammar for several years and only then beginning to read simple works. This method “which in Java can still be called new-fashioned, appears to have been in vogue in Aceh for a long time past... The student in Aceh begins by struggling through a mountain of grammatical matter.”²⁶ He mentioned that the grammar books were translated from Arabic to Malay (likely employing the interlinear

23 Hurgronje, *Mekka*, 283–284.

24 Christiaan Snouck Hurgronje, *The Acehnese*, vol. 2, trans. A.W.S. O’Sullivan (E.J. Brill, 1906), 5–7.

25 Hurgronje, *The Acehnese*, 6–7.

26 Hurgronje, *The Acehnese*, 7.

method but this is not stated) and he noted the difficulty for local Muslims for whom Acehese, not Malay, was the mother tongue, and that most therefore did not complete their elementary studies. As in his earlier scholarship Snouck here prioritized the value of the Meccan method of studying Arabic but he did not provide historical evidence for the claim that it “appears to have been” practiced in Aceh “for a long time,” just as he neglected to prove that the other method was used “since ancient times” by Javanese and Sundanese Muslims. The former claim may have been true, in which case the method may have indeed been brought to Aceh earlier than to Java, and Aceh’s ties with the Middle East, due to its location and particular history may have proved stronger that the influence of traditions practiced on neighboring islands, however no details are offered on how and when the method arrived or developed in Aceh.

Also towards the end of the 19th century, in 1886, Van den Berg published his by now famous study of Islamic education on the islands of Java and Madura in which he listed many of the religious books studied at the time in the *pesantren*.²⁷ He only mentioned interlinear translation once, when discussing how certain sections of Islamic jurisprudence texts were typically not taught (for example the sections on criminal law and slavery), and therefore the interlinear translations for these sections were often lacking.²⁸ From this extremely brief mention one has the impression that Van den Berg was aware of the translation practice (and he must have seen many such translations while touring the *pesantren*) as the implication was that other sections of such texts, which were taught, did have interlinear translations and notes, but he treated them matter-of-factly, so much so that they were not worthy of mention. Van den Berg also described lessons he witnessed as consisting of the reading of an Arabic book, sentence by sentence, with an explanation in the vernacular offered by the teacher. The explanation usually took the form of translation but at times additional clarification was given based on other works.²⁹ This may have been a depiction of the use of interlinear translation but it is not discussed.

Another example that gives insight on interlinear translation as a pedagogical method, but was written from a different perspective (yet in Dutch), is Achmad Djajadiningrat’s early 20th century account of life in a *pesantren*.³⁰ It depicted an episode in the life of Wardi, the young son of the district chief (*wedana*) of Banten in west Java who was sent to live as a student in a *pesantren* (*santri*) away from home.³¹ The *kyai*—the religious scholar heading the *pesantren*—asked what Wardi knew and when he replied that he could only recite the Qur’an the *kyai* said he will need to start with *Sittien*, referring to the popular Shāfi‘ī jurisprudence

27 L. W. C. van den Berg, “Het Mohammedaansche Godsdienstonderwijs op Java en Madoera en de daarbij Gebruikte Arabische Boeken,” *Tijdschrift voor Indische Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 31 (1886): 518–555.

28 Van den Berg, “Het Mohammedaansche Godsdienstonderwijs,” 533.

29 Van den Berg, “Het Mohammedaansche Godsdienstonderwijs,” 524.

30 Achmad Djajadiningrat, “Het Leven in een Pasantren,” *Tijdschrift voor het Binnenlandsch Betuur*, no. 34 (1908): 1–22.

31 Djajadiningrat, who was the the regent (*bupati*) of Serang from 1901–1917, was apparently writing his own memories of his brief childhood stay at a *pesantren*, see Zamakhsyari Dhofier, *Tradisi Pesantren. Studi Pandangan Hidup Kyai dan Visinya Mengenai Masa Depan Indonesia* (LP3ES, 2011), 39.

work *al-Sittin Mas'ala*. The kyai then summoned his advanced student to meet Wardi and asked the student to “write a *Sittien* for him, but without *logat*; he needs to get used to difficulties at once.” Djajadiningrat added a footnote for *logat*: *interlineaire vertaling* (interlinear translation).³²

This seems to imply that Wardi would need to fill in the translation as he made progress. In the classes, that took place in the mosque, beginners sat in front and moved gradually to the back as they progressed. The santris repeated the Javanese translation of the Arabic one by one, in a Javanese that was described as a very different and difficult form of the language than what was habitually used (a point also made by Snouck Hurgronje, see above). The kyai translated the Arabic into Javanese, explained and gave examples, yet the author noted that many students were forced to quit after studying *Sittien* as diligence was insufficient for success and very few reached the level of studying Arabic texts on doctrine and law. It is a brief description, in which studying interlinear translations of Islamic texts was portrayed as a completely routine part of everyday pesantren life and the practice of translation was not addressed in any specific way. Perhaps it can be understood implicitly that this pedagogical system did not suffice for most beyond a very basic level, as Snouck Hurgronje too suggested in his writings. It is also possible that, constituting such a routine pedagogy, no need was felt to describe it, and it was thus transparent also for a Javanese author who wrote about Islamic education, similar to the European scholars' approach.

In addition to Dutch and Indonesian writings on the topic French scholarship about it was also produced. In a 1904 article titled “A Malay interlinear translation of al-Sanūsī's *'Aqīda*” Antoine Cabaton discussed a 1893 Arabic to Malay interlinear translation of al-Sanūsī's *al-'Aqīda* belonging to al-Hajj Ismā'īl, a Malay imam of Cochinchina, and produced a French translation of this work.³³ As background Cabaton mentioned that the Malays in Cham, as opposed to local Muslims, were more orthodox in their practice and possessed manuscripts of the Qur'an, hadith, tafsir and various works on Islam's precepts. Of the manuscript he wrote that it contained the Arabic text, quite correct at the beginning but full of spelling mistakes towards the end, and an interlinear Malay version of the *'Aqīda*, a work on scholastic theology that, he noted, was held in very high esteem by Muslims.³⁴

Cabaton went on to explain that he found it unnecessary to reproduce the Arabic text, although it differed in several ways from the one published by Wolff in 1848, because it was identical to that which was printed in Cairo in 1901. Additionally, he noted, there were also copies of the work in France's national library.³⁵ This section, in which he laid out his reasons for not reproducing the Arabic source, is the only one in the article referring to it. So, although “interlinear translation” appears in the article's title it is quite marginal to this study. Cabaton did mention that “Our manuscript... which slavishly reproduces the Arabic original, is a curious specimen of the numerous interlinear translations of Arabic works made by the

32 Djajadiningrat, “Het Leven in een Pasantren,” 5.

33 Antoine Cabaton, “Traduction interlinéaire malaise de La 'Aqida d'Al-Senūsī,” *Journal Asiatique* (1904): 115–145.

34 Cabaton, “Traduction interlinéaire malaise,” 116.

35 Cabaton, “Traduction interlinéaire malaise,” 117.

Malays,” but did not elaborate on why he made this claim. He also commented on how literal the translation method was in its attempt to replicate the Arabic, so that “if the syntax is therefore a little tormented, it does not result in any obscurity.” Finally, he noticed that Arabic technical terms were conserved, but care was almost always taken to render them by Malay equivalents preceded by the word *artinya* (“the meaning is”, “this means”).³⁶

In a further, very brief article, Cabaton again discussed the Muslims of Cochinchina and the importance of the *ʿAqīda* amongst them, and mentioned the interlinear translation of the text he had encountered. This article examined a “table” that Cabaton believed was a summary of a “more developed dogmatic work” and formed part of Islamic education for the Chams.³⁷ He suspected it was based on al-Samarqandi, and very much abbreviated because its audience required the most basic doctrine. The text was copied by the same Malay of Cochinchina mentioned above, the imam al-Hajj Ismāʿīl. Here too there was no engagement with interlinear translation, which is not mentioned, even though in the article’s last two pages there are several examples of the genre.³⁸ Cabaton seemed more interested in the content and in a discrepancy he perceived between the teachings and the actions of local Muslims.

In a third instance of work on an interlinear translation Cabaton published an article on a Malay telling of the story of Raden Paku, otherwise known as Sunan Giri, one of the nine *walis* said to have converted Java to Islam.³⁹ That telling was in fact the Malay translation which had appeared in between the lines of a Javanese text but Cabaton was studying and translating (into French) the Malay only. He argued that from the point of view of language and style the legend of Sunan Giri “has the defects of all interlinear translations of its kind: obscurity and inclusion of Javanese words.” He was also critical of the Malay version for containing “numerous lacunae” and he viewed it as a clumsy adaptation of a more developed narrative.⁴⁰ More generally, Cabaton here was not interested in the interlinear aspect of the text but only in the biography of Sunan Giri, one viewed as central to the historiography of Java’s Islamization. The three articles by Cabaton, taken together, point to his awareness of the interlinear translation practice in both Cochinchina and Java and to his acquaintance with at least several such manuscripts, but not to an interest in the practice per se. Rather, his focus lay in the history and content of the texts.

Returning to Dutch scholarship, Pigeaud, in his book on Javanese folk performance mentioned a compilation of *mauluds*, printed in Bombay, in Arabic with Javanese interlinear glosses.⁴¹ The language, he wrote, was “the peculiar Javanese written in unvocalized Arabic

36 Cabaton, “Traduction interlinéaire malaise,” 120.

37 Antoine Cabaton, “Un abrégé malais du Catéchisme musulman,” *T’oung Pao* 5, no. 2 (1904): 157–164.

38 Antoine Cabaton, “Un abrégé malais,” 163–164.

39 Antoine Cabaton, “Raden Paku, Sunan de Giri (légende musulmane javanaise): Texte malais, traduction française et notes,” *Revue de l’histoire des religions*, no. 54 (1906): 374–400.

40 Cabaton, “Raden Paku,” 377.

41 Th. Pigeaud, *Javaanse Volksvertoningen. Bijdrage tot de Beschrijving van Land en Volk* (Batavia: Volkslectuur, 1938). *Mauluds* are panegyrics on the Prophet Muhammad, recited on the anniversary of his birth and other occasions. On the issue of terminology (i.e., “translation” vs. “gloss”), see below.

script from the old-fashioned religious schools (pesantrens).”⁴² Pigeaud went on to explain that for those unfamiliar with it, this Javanese was almost impossible to understand, especially because “it wishes to represent all Arabic phrases, including plurals and articles,” referring to the literalness of this translation method and to its striving to replicate the Arabic as closely as possible. When, however, one has become somewhat accustomed to this form of Javanese, he believed it was a fairly easy and reliable means of acquainting oneself with the contents of the Arabic texts and their highly elaborate vocabulary. Pigeaud noted that there were additional Arabic textbooks printed with Javanese interlinear glosses and that such works exercised an influence on the development of the Javanese language and the definition of commonly-used words. He offered an example from the *Sarpoel Anam (Maulud Sharaf al-Anām)* noting not only the word-for-word Javanese translation but also the use of certain inserted Javanese “code words” that indicated the grammatical position of a word within the sentence or a function like number (e.g., an indication of the plural form).⁴³

Pigeaud touched in this brief passage upon several key issues related to interlinear translation including its emerging availability in print, its literalness and detail, its effectiveness in conveying the Arabic source text, the existence of an internal system of “code words” that assisted in understanding Arabic syntax, and the translations’ impact on Javanese. Although he did not delve on these matters in this instance it is clear that he was deeply familiar with the interlinear translation paradigm and, indeed, in his later work and especially in his catalogue of Javanese literature published thirty years later, he would discuss many such texts in relative detail.

I have offered several examples of writings on interlinear translation from the second half of the 19th century and the first decades of the 20th. Among writings from this period there are also “non-examples” to note, by which I refer to scholars who wrote surveys or studies of particular regions in the archipelago with descriptions of everything from geography to cooking to religion, or more specifically studies about Islam, but did not mention interlinear translation as a pedagogical, cultural or religious practice.⁴⁴

An important example of scholarship that may be positioned in between studies that discussed interlinear translation and those that did not is Brumund’s 1857 book on public education among the Javanese.⁴⁵ It was the earliest study of Islamic education (and other educational systems) in colonial Indonesia, written with the stated goal of better understanding ideas and practices of education in Java.⁴⁶ The book purported to offer a

42 Th. Pigeaud, *Javaanse Volksvertoningen*, 290. The unvocalized Arabic script used to write Javanese is known as *gundhul* (bald, hairless).

43 Th. Pigeaud, *Javaanse Volksvertoningen*, 290–292.

44 Antoine Cabaton, *Java, Sumatra and the Other Islands of the Dutch East Indies*, trans. Bernard Miall (T.F. Unwin, 1911); William Marsden, *The History of Sumatra, Containing an Account of the Government, Laws, Customs, and Manners of the Native Inhabitants, with A Description of the Natural Productions, and A Relation of the Ancient Political State* (London: Printed for the Author, 1783); Guillaume F. Pijper, *Fragmenta Islamica. Studiën over her Islamisme in Nederlandsch Indië* (E.J. Brill, 1934); Thomas Stamford Raffles, *The History of Java in Two Volumes* (London: Black, Farbury and Allen, 1817).

45 J.F.G. Brumund, *Het Volksonderwijs onder de Javanen* (Batavia: Van Haren Noman & Kolff, 1857).

46 There were earlier reports and studies on a smaller scale, e.g., the 1831 government report on native

detailed overview of pesantren education yet it did not engage with the widespread practice of interlinear translation and, more generally, the author was unable to learn much of substance of the Javano-Islamic pedagogical system. For example, in a section describing the *langgars* (small houses of worship and study where youngsters often begun their educational journey), Brumund wrote that “it is said that there are thirteen Korans, at least parts of the Koran translated into Javanese and written with Arabic characters. I have never come across them. In Samarang, I am told that someone saw an Arabic Koran with an interlinear partial Javanese translation. Another was recently discovered elsewhere.”⁴⁷ Discussing the students at a pesantren in Langkong he claimed that they were taught to read and write Arabic “more or less mechanically” and that they “usually do not understand anything of what they read; now and then the haji gives the meaning and through this they then get some understanding, but very imperfect, incomplete and inaccurate.”⁴⁸ The author repeatedly mentioned his surprise and dismay that the kyais he met did not seem to know anything or be able to explain to him what he wanted to hear, about their institutions, text books and pedagogy, but he also mentioned he had only basic Malay (and this while studying a Javanese system) and it did not seem to occur to him that the kyais may not have wanted to engage with him on religious matters. His approach to what he found was summed up well in the following statement: “Whichever pesantren you visit, they can only show you the Koran, which they do not understand, as well as the kitabs, which contain a number of prescriptions of dry and burdensome religious ceremonies.”⁴⁹ Brumund’s study points to some of the limits of colonial research during this period: barriers of language, the difficulty of attaining certain types of information and an ideological bias that prevented him from seeing anything useful or productive in this particular system. As far as interlinear translations go, he was aware of their existence and possibly also of their use in some cases, and he made many assumptions about the pedagogical institutions in which these translations played a major role, but he was unable to gain access to them, both physically and in terms of the translations’ significance.

Where are the Interlinear Translations? Part II: Manuscript Catalogues

In addition to articles and books, a separate yet related body of works to examine when considering scholarship on interlinear translation are catalogues of Indonesian manuscripts. Such catalogues, assembled since around the mid-19th century, were sometimes written by colonial scholar-administrators, often the same figures who also wrote articles and books about their findings (e.g., Van der Tuuk). Catalogues, by definition, categorize the manuscripts according to certain criteria (be it language, region, collector, topic, genre, etc.)

educational institutions in Java, cited in Dhofier, *Tradisi Pesantren*, 64. On this history of native education see also J.A. van der Chijs, “Bijdragen tot de Geschiedenis van het Inlandsch Onderwijs in Nederlandsch-Indië. Aan officiële bronnen ontleend,” *Tijdschrift voor Indische Taal-, Land en Volkenkunde*, no. 16 (1864): 212–323.

47 Brumund, *Het Volksonderwijs onder de Javanen*, 13.

48 Brumund, *Het Volksonderwijs onder de Javanen*, 19.

49 Brumund, *Het Volksonderwijs onder de Javanen*, 25.

and tend to offer only brief information. In both early and more recent catalogues interlinear translation does not form a category of analysis or of listing. At times the existence of such a translation is not even mentioned in item descriptions or is mentioned as such with little detail or none at all.

For example, in a recent catalogue of manuscripts from West Kalimantan, a compilation of Arabic grammatical texts is described as written in the Arabic language and Arabic script without noting that it contains an interlinear translation into Javanese. The number of lines per page is noted as between five to nine, thus discounting the lines of translation. Interestingly, when the opening lines of the manuscript are quoted as part of the entry, the Arabic appears followed by the Javanese translation in parentheses, including the Javanese “code word” *utawi* that in such translations signals the subject of the Arabic nominal sentence.⁵⁰ A reader familiar with the interlinear model might well recognize these brief lines as indicating the existence of an interlinear translation of the grammatical work but for others it is only the photo of the manuscript page that clarifies this fact (see Fig. 3). Since most catalogue entries do not include a photo, the likelihood of missing relevant items is not negligible.⁵¹ However, it is important to note that in some cases an interlinear translation (*terjemahan antarbaris*) is explicitly noted while in others there is mention of two languages, e.g., Arabic and Malay, but the conjunction “and” remains ambiguous as there are various ways in which a text can be composed of two languages and interlinear translation is but one of them.

Whether or not the addition of an interlinear translation to a text or several texts within a bound manuscript was noted by the catalogue compiler or not would certainly have an effect on the availability of such texts for study and even of the awareness of their existence by future generations of scholars. And even if scholars wished to study the phenomenon it was often difficult to locate and assess the relevant texts based on the catalogues. An in-depth discussion of this aspect is beyond my scope but I will offer one example in order to make the point.⁵²

In the descriptive, four-volume catalogue of Balinese, Javanese and Sasak manuscripts in Van der Tuuk’s collection published by Brandes beginning in 1901 there are 1658 items in total and only four mentions of interlinear translations (three in volume 1, one in volume 2, none in volumes 3 and 4).⁵³ How to explain this? The issue of noticing and/or mentioning

50 On the historical development of the use of *utawi* see Muhammad Dluha Lutfillah’s article in the present issue.

51 Titik Pudjiastuti, ed. *Naskah-naskah Koleksi Masyarakat Indonesia Tengah Pontianak-Kalimantan Barat* (Perpusnas Press, 2020), 33–34. For additional examples see p. 60, 80.

52 There are several notable exceptions, all relatively recent, among them the catalogues compiled by Pigeaud, Florida, and Ricklefs, Voorhoeve and Gallop, all of whom paid attention to the interlinear phenomenon and noted it, often with precision and nuance. As noted above other catalogues, including the one for West Kalimantan, also documented interlinear translation, but at times inconsistently.

53 J. Brandes, *Beschrijving der Javaansche, Balineesche en Sasaksche Handschriften aangetroffen in de nalatenschap van Dr. H. N. van der Tuuk, en door hem vermaakt aan de Leidsche Universiteitsbibliotheek*, 4 delen (Batavia en Weltevreden: Landsdrukkerij, 1901–1926).

Fig. 3 Kompilasi Tata Bahasa Arab (Arabic Grammar Compilation), Abdurrahman Husein al-Falugha Collection, Pontianak, West Kalimantan BAH/17/AHF/I/PON. In Pudjiastuti 2020: 34.

interlinear translation is in part an issue of the terminology employed in scholarship and all the more so in catalogues that dedicate little space to each manuscript, and so the question of whether “interlinear” or a related term appears at all in a concise entry signals the difference between knowing, as a reader, that a text was interlinear (or followed a similar model) or not being aware of the fact. There has been a great deal of variability in terminology related to the interlinear practice, i.e., translation, glosses, interpretation, commentary and notes, which makes even searchable catalogues and databases difficult to assess and use for the purpose of identifying interlinear translations. The variety of terms reflects, in addition to idiosyncratic choices by compilers, perceptions of translation that have shifted over time and the ways different languages depict the practice: the complexity of what might seem like “translation” but upon a closer look branches off into glosses, notes, interpretation, *maarti* or *kitab gandhul*.⁵⁴ In order to better assess the actual number of interlinear texts in Brandes’

⁵⁴ The latter two terms are examples of indigenous terminology that in no way engages with the idea of lines. *Maarti* (Balinese, to give meaning) refers to typically Old Javanese to Balinese translations of Indic texts that are inscribed on palm leaves (*lontar*), with small dots connecting between original and translation; *kitab gandhul* refers to Javanese translation between the lines of an Arabic text in which the

catalogue one would need to search for these different terms, and likely additional ones, closely examine the possibly-relevant entries, and reach tentative conclusions as a truly clear picture would be unlikely to emerge based on the available information.⁵⁵

Preliminary Thoughts: Interlinear Translation and Scholarship on Indonesia

This article emerged out of interest in how interlinear translation in the Indonesian-Malay world had been studied, especially early on, and what assumptions about it might have been inherited by those studying this phenomenon in the present. My initial search for secondary sources did not produce much, and so the question remained: where are the interlinear texts, and writings about them, hiding within scholarship on Indonesia?

The examples discussed, on the whole, do not point to much interest in interlinear translation, even among scholars writing about Islamic manuscripts and educational contexts. Mine was by necessity a partial and rather tentative sample. Still, I believe it needs to be viewed within the general, broad scholarship produced about Indonesian religious and literary writings during the particular time period and also beyond it: interlinear translations, despite their abundance, the wealth of linguistic, historical and cultural information they can offer, and their importance as a method of teaching, learning and transmitting religious-textual traditions, including from early on in the process of Islamization in the Indonesian-Malay world, have been little studied. This is especially striking when considered within the broader framework of (primarily Dutch) colonial and postcolonial philology which produced numerous, and often systematic textual and linguistic studies of Indonesian writings.⁵⁶ Even studies that focused on translations from Arabic into Malay, or the influence of Arabic on the Malay language, tended to ignore or marginalize the interlinear model.⁵⁷ The compilers of

Javanese words “hang” or “dangle” (*gandhul*) from the Arabic ones.

- 55 In the more recent past, with many collections undergoing digitization, the availability of images makes things clearer, however even then searches are hampered by the use of multiple terms and, in some repositories, the neglect to employ “interlinear” as a descriptive category. Filtering collections by the number of languages appearing in a manuscript, sometimes the only hint that interlinearity may be present, is insufficient and produces many “false positives” that are not interlinear.
- 56 Examples include J. Gonda, *Sanskrit in Indonesia* (International Academy of Indian Culture, 1952); C. Hooykaas, *The Old-Javanese Ramayana Kakawin with Special Reference to the Problem of Interpolation in Kakawins* (Martinus Nijhoff, 1955); William Marsden, *A Grammar of the Malayan Language, with an introduction and praxis* (London: Cox and Baylis, 1812); Th. Pigeaud, *Literature of Java*, 4 volumes (Martinus Nijhoff, 1967–1980); A. Teeuw, *Modern Indonesian Literature*, 2 volumes (Martinus Nijhoff, 1967, 1979); H. N. van der Tuuk, “Kort verslag van de Maleische handschriften in het East India House te Londen,” *Tijdschrift voor Nederlandsch-Indie*, no. 1 (1849): 385–405; E.M. Uhlenbeck, “Beknopte Javaansche grammatica (Concise Javanese Grammar)” (Volkslectuur, 1941); E.M. Uhlenbeck, “A Critical Survey of Studies on the Languages of Java and Madura” (Martinus Nijhoff, 1964); P. J. Zoetmulder, *Kalangwan: A Survey of Old Javanese Literature* (Martinus Nijhoff, 1974).
- 57 G. W. J. Drewes, “The History of the Malay Language: A Preliminary Survey,” *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 115, no. 2 (1959): 138–156; Cyril Skinner, “The Influence of Arabic on Modern Malay (with particular reference to spoken Malay),” In *Cyril Skinner (1924–1986). Orientalist, Linguist,*

dictionaries produced for multiple Indonesian languages also seem to have disregarded the interlinear texts as an important source even though the interlinear text can itself be viewed as a dictionary, offering a source and method to trace the history of words and their meanings.⁵⁸ One exception (although not in the sphere of Islamic texts) was Van der Tuuk, who included many examples from Balinese *maarti* texts in his trilingual Old Javanese-Balinese-Dutch dictionary (1897–1912).⁵⁹ Catalogues, as noted above, were also for the most part not fruitful sources for locating and studying interlinear translations. In part this was due to the variability of terminology which makes even searchable catalogues and databases difficult to assess and use for this purpose and, more generally, it seems that interlinear translation was often not considered as a vital dimension of manuscripts, worthy of elaboration or even mention. I suggest that the fact they were difficult to locate in catalogues, used as an important resource by scholars, contributed to cementing their relative “invisibility.”

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The gaps and silences in what can be termed “the interlinear archive,” presented in a preliminary manner in this article, make writing about it challenging as it is more difficult to write about and explain gaps in, and fragments of, scholarship, than to engage with more fully available sources, and perhaps many others are out there awaiting discovery and analysis. In addition, regarding what I called “non-examples,” that is surveys of Indonesia (focusing on regions or themes) that make no mention of interlinear translation, it is always possible and probable that their authors’ interest lay elsewhere, or that language barriers hampered their efforts.⁶⁰ However, if we assume that the examples presented do add up to something, I make several suggestions below as to why interlinear translations have not been studied or documented more extensively.

Can we detect here, as has been more generally proposed regarding colonial Dutch scholarship, a bias towards the Hindu-Buddhist and away from the Islamic? The approach or lack thereof towards interlinear texts may have been part of the trend, i.e., an enduring interest

Historian, Scholar. A Collection of Essays and Reviews, ed. Corfield, J. (Monash Asia Institute, 1996): 3–20.

- 58 William Marsden, *A Dictionary of the Malayan Language, in two parts, Malayan and English and English and Malayan* (London: Cox and Baylis, 1812); B. F. Matthes, *Boegineesch-Hollandsch woordenboek met Hollandsch-Boegineesch woordenlijst* (Den Haag: Martinus Nijhoff, 1874); J. Pijnappel, *Maleisch-Hollandsch Woordenboek*, 3rd edition (Amsterdam: Frederik Muller, 1884); J. Rigg, *A Dictionary of the Sunda Language of Java* (Batavia: Lange and Co., 1862); R.J. Wilkinson, *A Malay-English Dictionary*, 2 vols. (Kelly and Walsh, 1901; Macmillan & Co., 1959).
- 59 H.N. van der Tuuk, *Kawi-Balinesch-Nederlands Woordenboek* (Batavia: Landsdrukkerij, 1897–1912). According to Teeuw van der Tuuk “paid much attention” throughout his research to Balinese “interlinear translations, explanations and comments” within Old Javanese texts. In an 1871 letter van der Tuuk referred to such manuscripts he had encountered as “innumerable.” A. Teeuw, “Van der Tuuk as lexicographer,” *Archipel*, no. 51 (1996) 126. Whereas this article focuses for the most part on scholarship related to Islamic interlinear translations, a comparison with non-Islamic such translations from Indonesia is warranted.
- 60 As for language competence, the need to know both Arabic and an Indonesian language in order to read interlinear texts, many of the Dutch colonial scholars studied Arabic in addition to at least one Indonesian language as part of their training. Some scholar-administrators, e.g., Sir Stamford Thomas Raffles who wrote extensively about literature, relied on local informants.

in the ruins of temples, ancient sculpture, the role of Sanskrit in Old Javanese poetry, Islam as a “thin veneer” covering prior traditions as well as a deep-seated anxiety about Islam.⁶¹ Although interlinear translation was widespread in particular places, above all in the Islamic educational sphere, it seems to have often remained unseen.⁶² This approach was evident, for example, in Brumund’s book where, discussing the study of Arabic texts, he posed the questions: “is all of this something more than mechanical teaching? What is taught for the cultivation of the intellect, for the ennoblement of the heart, and the sanctification of life; what to inculcate in them pure concepts of God and religion, and to make them feel for them?” More generally, he viewed the pesantren as “institutions, established to complete the work of destruction of mind and heart...”⁶³ These quotes point to an approach which saw Islam as a debilitating religion, the method of Islamic teachings as technical and superficial and Arabic as almost unattainable, whereas the author praised traditional (i.e., non-Islamic) Javanese literature for its beauty and its being filled with educational and religious prescriptions that, according to Brumund, were deliberately not included in the pesantren curriculum because the kyais preferred their disciples to be ignorant so they could remain in power.⁶⁴

On the point of a certain invisibility of interlinear translations I would add that further to the question of scholarship’s approaches to Islam, it is interesting that texts that have a prominent visual aspect—text and translation often written in different-sized or colored script, multi-directional writing on the page, note-filled margins—are invisible or barely visible in the scholarship. That their visibility has not called much attention to them reveals a blind spot of traditional philology that has privileged textual analysis to the point of ignoring other major dimensions of the manuscripts.⁶⁵

It also seems, based on the evidence so far, that interlinear translation was taken at face value, or taken for granted as a convenient way to translate, to transfer meaning efficiently from one language to another. If it was but a technical device without much depth and with

61 For a literary work in which Islam is portrayed as a hidden danger, lurking in the shadows of Dutch colonial life and threatening to overcome it, see Louis Couperus, *De Stille Kracht* (Amsterdam: L.J. Veen, 1900), translated into English by Alexander Teixeira de Mattos under the title *The Hidden Force*.

62 This argument would be strengthened by showing that, on the contrary, traditions of non-Islamic and especially Hindu-Buddhist interlinear translation were studied more extensively during this period. Such a comparative study has yet to be undertaken but, for now, to support the claim I suggest that (1) interlinear translation was used most widely in Islamic circles and so that is where most sources could be found and (2) a towering figure like Van der Tuuk, who was interested in Christian, Hindu-Buddhist and other non-Islamic cultures, and who was also familiar with Islamic interlinear texts (see above), did not disregard but rather was fascinated by Balinese interlinear translations and incorporated many of them into his dictionary.

63 Brumund, *Het Volksonderwijs onder de Javanen*, 24.

64 Brumund, *Het Volksonderwijs onder de Javanen*, 26. In the same section Javanese literature is also described as “a product of licentious imagination and excessive sensuality” yet nevertheless containing the above praiseworthy traits.

65 For an analysis that attempts to challenge this blind spot see Ronit Ricci, “Implicit Comparisons: Visuality and the Interlinear Manuscript Page,” *History and Theory*, published online 16 September 2025, <https://doi.org/10.1111/hith.70002>.

no significant implications what more was there to say about it?⁶⁶ This approach is evident today if students and teachers in Islamic boarding schools are asked if there is reason to study the practice, and it may have been also prevalent in the past and conveyed to European scholars who showed an interest or who came across interlinear texts. Such an approach was apparent, for example, in Juynboll's articles discussed above in which he only translated and analyzed an Arabic text, disregarding the translation. Interlinear texts may have also looked familiar to European scholars from their own world—the languages and the religion were different but the practice, especially for translating Latin into vernaculars, was well known in Europe for centuries. Could this explain why Dutch and British scholars, generally so interested in the details of Indonesia's cultures, and studying them so extensively, were not more curious?

Perhaps there were other reasons for interlinear translation not having been taken too seriously, besides its view as a technical device, that had to do with understandings of “translation.” As has been pointed out, terminologies for the practice as documented in articles and catalogues varied widely, suggesting that there was no agreement on whether the words between the lines constituted a translation (whatever the definition of this unruly term), or a commentary, gloss, interpretation, or explanatory notes, each of which could be understood differently on an epistemological level and valued or judged differently by scholars. The stark literalness of many Islamic interlinear translations, the effort to replicate the Arabic to the highest degree which produced clusters of words and sentences that were entirely unidiomatic, likely seemed like a pointless form of translation to some. It may also be, again within the broader sphere of colonial scholarship on Indonesian manuscripts and texts in which works were often evaluated based on their similarity (imagined or real) to earlier sources or Ur-texts, that the interlinear text could have been viewed as a form of interpolation: an unwanted, unwelcome addition that somehow contaminated the original, authentic text, in this case an Arabic one.⁶⁷

Scholars who were exceptions to the rule in their interest and in the studies they produced, above all Van Ronkel and Snouck Hurgronje, showed how those who did examine the practice of Islamic interlinear translation more closely discovered its complexity and its implications which were apparent in the linguistic, religious and social spheres. Van Ronkel, as a central example of producing in-depth scholarship, clearly engaged with many interlinear texts in order to reach the level of detail and nuance presented in his studies. He detected dimensions of the genre that others disregarded, missed or ridiculed, including the extreme literalness of the method that, having its own logic, prioritized single words over sentence comprehensibility; the type of vocabulary translated in interlinear texts; both common and

66 Returning to the translations' general invisibility, I note that convenience, efficiency and precision, usually associated during the colonial period with the Dutch, and much less so with Indonesians, was disregarded, or rendered invisible when it was accomplished, and on a large scale, by native translators.

67 Much of the scholarship that claims “interpolation” on the part of Indonesian writers is focused on Indian civilization-derived texts, see, for example, R. Ng. Poerbatjaraka, “Arjunawiwāha: Tekst en vertaling,” *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 82 (1926): 181–305; C. Hooykaas, *The Old Javanese Rāmāyana Kakawin with Special Reference to the Problem of Interpolation in Kakawins* (Martinus Nijhoff, 1950).

unusual forms of rendering Arabic into Malay; and the source of much of the Arabic vocabulary adapted into Malay about which he dropped some hints but did not explicitly discuss. Snouck Hurgronje noted and described the differences between two methods of studying Arabic texts by Indonesians from various regions of the archipelago at home and in Mecca, offering a glimpse into the ethnic, linguistic, and social aspects of adhering to these practices. The work of these scholars (and other, more recent ones whose studies lie beyond the scope of this article) points to the richness of interlinear translations as a research topic and to the many yet unanswered questions about them that await investigation.

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